

Time in nature is associated with reduced inequalities in child mental wellbeing: evidence from global positioning system (GPS) data.

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Summary

Natural environments may benefit child mental wellbeing whilst offering a lever for reducing inequalities, but methodological biases mean evidence is mixed. We used global positioning system data from children (n=636) to measure daily percentage of time in nature and linked this to mental wellbeing outcomes to examine moderation by sex and socioeconomic position (SEP). We found increased time in nature was associated with reduced likelihood of externalising (i.e. behavioural) difficulties in all children (OR 0.909, 95% CI 0.831—0.995, p=0.039). This effect was moderated by SEP (p=0.037), suggesting time in nature benefits those from deprived backgrounds more than advantaged peers.

KEYWORDS: time-weighted GPS, activity space, greenspace exposure, effect moderation, socioeconomic status / position

1. Introduction

Exposure to natural environments has been associated with improved mental health outcomes in children and adolescents (McCormick 2017; Tillmann et al. 2018; Twohig-Bennett & Jones 2018), including increased academic performance (Wu et al. 2014); lower rates of depression, anxiety, and stress (Amoly et al., 2014); and reductions in social, emotional, and behavioural problems (Tillmann et al., 2018; Richardson et al., 2017; Markevych et al. 2014). However, the evidence is mixed, with almost half of 35 studies reviewed by Tillman et al. (2018) reporting no statistical significance between nature and mental health outcomes in children. This may be because most studies have measured nature exposure based on residential neighbourhood, or retrospectively from recall surveys (Hartig et al. 2014). Residential neighbourhood is typically characterised using fixed geographies around the home (e.g., distance buffers, administrative units), which may fail to capture heterogenous exposure within an individual's 'activity space' (Kwan 2012). Whereas bias between self-reported measures and objective measures has long been identified as a weakness of recall surveys (Coughlin 1990).

Methodological bias limits our understanding of the underlying mechanisms between nature and health (Markevych et al. 2017), which is vital for identifying who might benefit more (or less) from the relationship (Hartig et al. 2014). The strength and direction of pathways can depend on factors such as socioeconomic position (SEP), sex/gender, and ethnicity (Markevych et al. 2017). Indeed, increasing evidence suggests that nature exposure benefits some sociodemographic groups more than others, so it

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is important that study designs consider effect moderation (Rigolon et al. 2021). In this preliminary study, we aim to address these methodological limitations by examining the association between nature exposure and child mental wellbeing using objective and direct measures of nature exposure. We use time-weighted global positioning system (GPS) data from a nationally representative sample of 10- and 11-year-old children in Scotland to measure mean daily percentage of time spent in nature. We then link this to indicators of mental wellbeing, sex, and socioeconomic position to answer two research questions: 1. Is spending time in nature beneficial to children's mental wellbeing? 2. Are effects moderated by sex or socioeconomic position?

2. Methodology

2.1. Study Sample

We used data from SPACES (Studying Physical Activity in Children's Environments across Scotland), whose participants were subsampled from Growing Up in Scotland (GUS); a longitudinal cohort study (n=5,217) that began in 2004. GUS sampling design ensured national representativeness across socioeconomic and geographical distributions of the Scottish population.

2.1. Outcomes

Child mental wellbeing was assessed with the parent-reported Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) obtained from GUS. The SDQ contains four difficulty domains, two of which are 'internalising' (Emotional Problems and Peer Problems) representing emotional difficulties, such as anxiety and depression. Two are 'externalising' (Conduct Problems and Hyperactivity) representing behavioural difficulties, such as aggression and disruption. Scores range 0—20, with higher scores indicate more difficulties. SDQ subscales were dichotomised as normal/borderline or abnormal (representing the most extreme 10% population).

2.1. Natural Space Exposure

In 2015—2016 SPACES participants wore a GPS device (Qstarz BTQ1000XT; Qstarz International Co., Ltd, Taiwan) recording location every 10 seconds during waking hours (5am—11pm) for eight consecutive days. Valid GPS locations (speed <27 ms⁻¹; dilution of precision <10) identified as being outdoors (Signal-To-Noise Ratio >200) were buffered by 2.6m (accuracy of devices in semi-open areas: Schipperijn et al. 2014) and spatially joined to natural landcovers using Ordnance Survey MasterMap (2015) using the 'Make' attribute of feature classification. The number of GPS exposed to nature (NS) was transformed into a percentage based on daily wear (total GPS per day). Daily percentage of time exposed was then averaged across days meeting our inclusion criteria of a minimum of 5-hours GPS (1880 points) per day.

2.2. Covariates

We used sex and household income as moderators. Household income (obtained from GUS) was dichotomised (low SEP/high SEP) at the national median for Scotland in 2016 (£22,918). Maternal age, total physical activity, residential urbanicity, and residential availability of nature (within 100m of home) were included as potential confounders. Season (winter/summer) in which GPS device was worn was included as a measurement control.

2.3. Statistical Analysis

We used univariate binomial regressions to compare time exposed by sex and SEP separately. We then fitted multivariable binomial regressions containing exposure (NS), moderators and covariates to each outcome separately. Effect moderation was quantified by including an interaction term with sex and SEP separately.

3. Results

A total of 636 children provided sufficient GPS data for analysis. Boys spent more time in nature than girls (13.7% CI 12.5—14.9% versus 11.6% CI 10.6—12.5%), but there was no variation by SEP (low 13.0 % CI 11.3—14.8%; high 12.3% CI 11.2—13.3%).

Odds ratios indicated an association between spending time in nature and reduced likelihood of abnormal externalising scores (OR 0.984: 95% CI 0.970 – 0.998: Table 1). There was no evidence of effect moderation by sex on either outcome, however there was moderation by SEP on Externalising difficulties ($p=0.037$). Examination of marginal plots indicated that spending more time in nature was associated with reduced likelihood of abnormal externalising scores for children from low SEP households, but had no effect on those from high SEP households (Figure 1). Low SEP children who spent 10—15% of each day in nature had a similar likelihood of externalising difficulties as those from high SEP households, whose likelihood of externalising difficulties remained low regardless of time in nature.

Table 1 Outputs from logistic regressions fit to binomial outcomes (1=abnormal SDQ score).

<i>Predictors</i>	Internalising Difficulties			Externalising Difficulties		
	<i>Odds Ratios</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Odds Ratios</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	0.210	0.008 – 5.206	0.334	0.000	0.000 – 0.048	0.002
Sex (Male)	1.090	0.341 – 3.484	0.883	4.699	0.985 – 22.410	0.052
SEP (Low)	2.119	0.799 – 5.620	0.128	1.463	0.402 – 5.327	0.557
Maternal age	0.991	0.917 – 1.072	0.821	1.087	0.987 – 1.197	0.089
Total PA	0.999	0.996 – 1.001	0.262	1.001	0.999 – 1.003	0.315
Urban (Urban)	0.413	0.130 – 1.314	0.131	2.037	0.596 – 6.961	0.251
Residential NS 100m	1.000	0.998 – 1.002	0.899	0.998	0.994 – 1.002	0.353
Season (Winter)	5.263	1.796 – 15.424	0.003	4.191	1.359 – 12.924	0.014
NS	0.927	0.859 – 1.001	0.053	0.909	0.831 – 0.995	0.039
Observations		636			636	
R ²		0.112			0.171	

Figure 1 Effect moderation by household income on Externalising Difficulties. Marginal effects plot indicating how the beneficial effects of spending time in nature on the likelihood of abnormal Externalising score are moderated by household income.

4. Discussion

We found that spending time in nature was associated with reduced likelihood of externalising difficulties (i.e., behavioural problems) in all children, but that beneficial associations were greatest for children from low SEP households. Children from high SEP households had a low risk of externalising difficulties regardless of time in nature. By contrast, low SEP children who made no use of nature had higher risk of externalising difficulties, but a reduction in risk was associated with low SEP children spending 10–15% of their day in nature.

Interest in the potential role that nature exposure may provide deprived populations has increased in recent years, particularly the potential to disrupt the usual pathways by which socioeconomic disadvantage is converted to health disadvantage (Rigolon et al. 2021). Exposure to nature is hypothesised to act along three (intertwining) pathways: mitigation - reducing environmental exposure (e.g., air pollution, noise, heat); instoration – opportunities for physical activity and social connection; and restoration – reducing stress and improving well-being (Markevych et al., 2017).

Externalising problems are characterised by aggression, impulsivity, and inattention. Time in nature may offer children from low SEP households with opportunities for restoration away from stressful environments or that enable them to manage their emotions. Similarly, the benefits could be tied to greater physical activity levels in nature building capacities in children to regulate emotion. Our observational, cross-sectional study precluded evaluation of causal mechanisms, but our results suggest that the pathways through which natural space exert their influence may differ by children’s social position.

We have presented preliminary results, but our future work will stratify time spent in nature at different levels of physical activity to see if accounting for moderation by physical activity gives associative support to restoration or instoration pathways.

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